

Open Data Sharing Checklist for Human Movement Sciences

Ethics, Consent, and Study Planning	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Compliance of study design with local regulations and ethical principles carefully considered and confirmed [Recs. A.1, A.2]*
<input type="checkbox"/>	Ethical approval granted [B.1]* <i>IRB/Ethics ID:</i> <i>IRB#ABC-12345</i>
<input type="checkbox"/>	Local data protection regulation framework identified [B.1]* <i>Framework:</i> <i>GDPR / HIPAA / FADP</i>
<input type="checkbox"/>	Written informed consent forms for participants finalised and approved [B.2, B.3]* See Consent Form Template provided: Link Forms include: <input type="checkbox"/> Data sharing option (specify whether e.g. extended, unspecified, etc.) <input type="checkbox"/> Opt-out options (future unspecified research / public repository deposit / commercial collaborations, etc.) <input type="checkbox"/> Right to withdraw consent, including timeline, clearly communicated <input type="checkbox"/> Jurisdiction-specific clarifications
<input type="checkbox"/>	De-identification method documented [B.6]* <i>Method:</i> <i>Pseudonymisation / Anonymisation</i>
<input type="checkbox"/>	Re-identification risk assessed and documented [Table 1]* <i>Risk level:</i> <i>Minimal / Low / Moderate</i>
<input type="checkbox"/>	Comprehensive (hierarchical) framework established to document metadata at source [Table 2]* [B.7, E.1, E.2, E.3, E.4]*
<input type="checkbox"/>	Data quality assessment (see Measurement Quality) [Table 3]*
Data Acquisition & Processing	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Written informed consent obtained from all participants [B.2, B.3]* See Consent Form Template provided: Link
<input type="checkbox"/>	Comprehensive metadata documented at source using hierarchical structure [Table 2]* [B.7, E.1, E.2, E.3, E.4]*
<input type="checkbox"/>	Personally identifiable information (PII) minimised [B.5]* E.g. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Age, not date of birth - Year, not full assessment date - Rounded values (nearest cm or kg) or BMI category
<input type="checkbox"/>	Sensitive PII (SPII) removed or appropriately protected [B.5]* E.g. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Any facial features blurred/masked or cropped out of video/images - Rare pathology sample sizes considered (e.g. only aggregated data shared)
<input type="checkbox"/>	Data standardisation/harmonisation efforts documented [B.4]* <i>Method:</i> <i>AAFACT / SPARTACUS / REFRAME</i>
<input type="checkbox"/>	Data quality assessment (see Completeness) [Table 3]*
Data Storage & Infrastructure	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Secure storage infrastructure meets legal requirements [C.1, C.2]* Consult the Data Management and IT Support teams at your institution. <i>Platform:</i> <i>ABC University's Secure Data Vault</i>
<input type="checkbox"/>	Access controls implemented (authentication, audit trails) Consult the Data Management and IT Support teams at your institution. <i>Access controls:</i> <i>MFA / SSO / Audit logging</i>
<input type="checkbox"/>	Long-term sustainability of data storage considered [B.8]*
Data Sharing	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Data FAIR ness carefully considered and confirmed [A.3]*
<input type="checkbox"/>	Only data with valid rights included (original collection or explicit permission) [D.1]*
<input type="checkbox"/>	License explicitly specified (incl. terms of use & attribution) [D.2]* <i>License:</i> <i>CC BY-SA</i>
<input type="checkbox"/>	Persistent identifier (DOI) assigned [D.3]* <i>DOI:</i> <i>https://doi.org/10.1000/182</i>
<input type="checkbox"/>	Data access agreement includes non-re-identification commitment [D.4]*
<input type="checkbox"/>	Author & institution contact details provided
<input type="checkbox"/>	Secure data sharing infrastructure used [C.1, C.2, C.3]* For generalist repositories, see the following comparison chart: Link <i>Repository:</i> <i>Zenodo</i>

* These recommendations and tables reference the guidelines provided in: *ISB, ESB, ESMAC, GCMAS, and ASB Guidelines for Open Data Sharing in the Human Movement Sciences*, Ortigas-Vásquez et al. XXXX

<input type="checkbox"/>	Equity and inclusivity in data sharing considered [C.4]* E.g. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Open-access repositories prioritised - Journals with no paywall for student/academic/non-commercial access favoured - Non-proprietary file formats included 		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Links to associated datasets provided	<i>Assoc. datasets:</i>	<i>https://doi.org/10.1000/XXX</i>
<input type="checkbox"/>	Processing code/algorithms made available (if applicable) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Persistent identifier assigned to code <input type="checkbox"/> License explicitly assigned to code <input type="checkbox"/> Versioning clearly specified 	<i>Repository:</i>	<i>GitHub</i>
		<i>DOI:</i>	<i>https://doi.org/10.1000/YYY</i>
		<i>License:</i>	<i>MIT License</i>
		<i>Version:</i>	<i>1.0</i>

Examples in grey are intended as guidance, not an exhaustive list of options.

* These recommendations and tables reference the guidelines provided in: *ISB, ESB, ESMAC, GCMAS, and ASB Guidelines for Open Data Sharing in the Human Movement Sciences*, Ortigas-Vásquez et al. XXXX